

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

5th TNA Call Documentation – User Report (User)

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

After the StoRIES Transnational Access stay or Virtual Access, users are required to submit a *User Report*. This should be done within 4 weeks after the Access is completed unless otherwise agreed. The *User Report* will be given to the User(s) by the Project Management. The report contains sections related to the work performed, the main results and observations that were achieved.

This document should be completed, signed, and sent to the following person, along with the *TNA Cost Claim Form* and all eligible receipts either by e-mail [REDACTED]

Summary questionnaire for users who have been granted Transnational Access (TNA) under the StoRIES project Horizon 2020 TNA scheme. More information on StoRIES TNA can be found in "[General Rules](#)" and in "[Access Policy](#)" which can be found on the StoRIES webpage.

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Investigation of Hybrid Thermal Energy Storage System
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	IHTESS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	KTH Energy Storage Research Infrastructure (KTH ESRI)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Hybrid energy storage, Thermal energy storage, latent heat, Sensible heat, numerical modelling
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	22/09/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	07/12/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	23/09/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	06/12/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	22
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	20 - Weekends, 2 – attending abroad event
Number of days using the RI	53
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	

User	
User group leader or sole applicant (user group member 1)	
First name	[REDACTED]
Last name	[REDACTED]
Affiliation / Employer	Khalifa University
Country of Employer	United Arab Emirates
E-mail	[REDACTED]
Comments	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
Please insert more fields if your groups had more than four members.	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	

Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)

The primary objective of this project is to numerically evaluate the performance a hybrid sensible-latent thermal energy storage (TES) system for high-temperature concentrated solar power (CSP) application. The storage consists of sensible and latent layers of materials embedded in a tank while using liquid sodium as a heat transfer fluid (HTF). By integrating sensible heat storage materials, such as quartzite and sand, with latent heat storage materials in the form of encapsulated phase change materials (PCMs), the system aims to achieve higher energy storage density and improved thermal performance while considering the economic perspective. A schematic diagram of the studied TES concept is shown in the figure below.

Figure 1 Scheme of the studied sensible and hybrid TES

The hybrid design seeks to highlight the strength points of both storage types: the cost-effectiveness of sensible materials and the high storage capacity and efficient isothermal heat transfer aspects of PCMs. The configuration strategically places PCMs near the outlet to stabilize the output temperature during charge and discharge and more importantly, ensure consistent energy delivery during discharge.

Indeed, the research aligns with the growing demand for advanced TES technologies to support renewable energy integration. Ultimately, the project aspires to provide a scalable and cost-effective TES solution for sustainable energy systems.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

Throughout the TNA period, several activities were performed. These activities can be classified into 5 main categories including:

1. Conceptualization

- Conducted an extensive review of current TES technologies, focusing on the integration of sensible and latent heat storage systems.
- Investigated the suitability of materials to be used as storage medium. This includes both sensible and latent heat materials

- Analyzed the compatibility of materials, including potential challenges such as corrosion.
- Designed a hybrid TES system incorporating layered PCM capsules within a packed bed of sensible fillers.
- Developed a layered configuration where PCM layer heights were optimized for improved thermal performance.

2. Numerical Modeling and Simulations

- Created MATLAB-based numerical model to simulate the thermal performance of the hybrid system under charging and discharging cycles.
- Validate the model based on two experimental datasets obtained from the available literature.
- Performed a mesh optimization study to determine the optimal mesh size, ensuring solution accuracy and independence while minimizing computational cost.
- Conducted simulation studies with a close look at the temperature profiles and liquid fraction evolution of PCMs to analyze the system's thermal behavior under varying operating conditions.

3. Performance Evaluation and Analysis

- Assessed the hybrid system's ability to stabilize the outlet fluid temperature and deliver heat with consistent temperature during discharge.
- Quantified thermal efficiency and energy storage density compared to conventional systems.
- Evaluated the trade-offs between material costs, system complexity, and performance enhancements.

4. Scientific field visits

- Lab tour and hands-on experience of latent heat TES, KTH, Sweden
- Lab tour Live-In Lab, KTH, Sweden
- Chilled water TES for district cooling, Stockholm Exergi, Sweden
- Underground TES with ground source heat pump, Stockholm University, Sweden
- Lab tour Karlsruhe Liquid Metal Laboratory, KIT, Germany

5. Reporting and Presentation

- Prepared and delivered detailed progress updates on weekly basis to research collaborators, highlighting key findings and challenges.
- Presented project results at a research seminar at the host institution.
- Drafted a research paper summarizing the conducted work and the outcomes of the project.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

To thoroughly evaluate the performance of the packed bed thermal energy storage (TES) system, a parametric study was conducted to analyze the effects of varying the packed bed configuration on key performance metrics. The study focused on four primary indicators: efficiency, cost, utilization ratio, and discharged energy. The analysis involved independently adjusting the volume fractions

of PCM1 (ζ_1) and PCM2 (ζ_2) within the range of 0 to 0.3 in increments of 0.01. The resulting performance trends are illustrated in Figure 2, providing valuable insights into the influence of PCM volume fractions on system performance.

Material Cost: Figure 2(a) shows that the material cost of the TES system ranges from approximately 9 to 27 \$/kWh. The lowest cost is observed in the fully sensible configuration, whereas increasing the volume fractions of PCM1 and PCM2 leads to higher costs. This rise is attributed to the higher material cost of PCMs, along with additional expenses related to encapsulation and fabrication. Notably, the rate of cost increase with PCM2 (ζ_2) is significantly steeper than with PCM1 (ζ_1) due to PCM2's higher density and a material cost approximately four times greater than PCM1. The red dashed line at $\zeta_2 = 0.09$ suggests an intermediate configuration that balances cost and performance. Along this line, the cost of PCM1 increases linearly with storage capacity, resulting in a nearly constant total cost as ζ_1 increases.

Efficiency: As depicted in Figure 2(b), efficiency decreases with the addition of either PCM1 or PCM2, with PCM2 having a more pronounced impact. This decline is primarily due to the slower heat transfer rate between the heat transfer fluid (HTF) and PCM2 during charging. Efficiency values range from 0.5 to 0.8, reflecting the trade-offs associated with PCM incorporation into the TES system.

Utilization Ratio: Figure 2(c) highlights the utilization ratio trends during charging and discharging. During charging, the utilization ratio increases with the addition of PCM1, while PCM2 has the opposite effect. The highest utilization ratios are observed in configurations with high ζ_1 and low ζ_2 , as the PCM1 layer improves energy storage within the desirable temperature range. During discharging, the addition of PCM2 enhances the utilization ratio, whereas PCM1 has a negative impact. This improvement is due to PCM2's melting point aligning with the desirable discharge temperature range. However, the average utilization ratio across charging and discharging shows no clear trend, as the opposing effects of PCM1 and PCM2 balance each other.

Discharged Energy: Figure 2(d) presents the total energy discharged from the TES system. The discharged energy increases with higher PCM volume fractions, particularly with ζ_2 , due to PCM2's higher heat content compared to PCM1. Configurations with low PCM fractions exhibit significantly lower discharged energy, as these rely primarily on the sensible storage medium, which has a comparatively limited energy density.

These findings underscore the trade-offs involved in incorporating PCMs into packed bed TES systems. While PCM1 improves performance during charging and PCM2 during discharging, their combined use may not always be advantageous for all applications. Tailoring configurations to specific operational needs, such as stabilizing the outlet HTF temperature during either charging or discharging, can optimize system performance while minimizing unnecessary complexity.

Figure 2 Parametric study contours for PCM volume fractions ranging from $\zeta_1=\zeta_2=0$ to $\zeta_1=\zeta_2=0.3$, with a porosity of 0.5, illustrating key performance indicators: (a) Material cost (b) Efficiency (c) Average utilization ratio and (d) Total released energy.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The conducted work presents a comprehensive numerical investigation into hybridizing sensible-based packed bed thermal energy storage (PBTES) by incorporating two types of encapsulated metallic-based phase change materials (PCMs), each positioned at opposite ends of the storage tank. This approach explores the potential performance enhancement of next-generation high-temperature concentrated solar power applications. The hybrid configuration leverages the latent heat of fusion and the near-isothermal phase change behavior of PCMs to enhance storage capacity and stabilize the outlet fluid temperature within desirable ranges. The PCMs were carefully selected to have appropriate melting temperatures. A validated concentric dispersion model was used to simulate a wide range of configurations with PCM layer thicknesses varying from 0 to 30%. Based on the results, the following key findings are drawn:

- Efficiency and utilization ratio are strongly influenced by PCM selection and distribution, with PCM1 enhancing charging performance and PCM2 improving discharging performance, underscoring the need for tailored designs based on specific operational requirements.
- While PCM integration enhances energy density, utilization ratio, and discharged energy, it increases costs and reduces efficiency, necessitating careful optimization to balance application priorities.

In conclusion, hybridizing sensible-based PBTES with PCMs has significant potential to enhance storage capacity and thermal stability for high-temperature applications. By optimizing PCM selection, configuration, and operating conditions, the trade-offs between cost, efficiency, and performance can be effectively managed to tailor the system for specific applications.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The TNA successfully advanced hybrid packed bed TES systems by integrating sensible and latent materials for high-temperature CSP applications. Key achievements include:

- **Hybrid Design:** Developed a novel configuration with PCM layers strategically placed to stabilize HTF temperature and enhance energy density.
- **Numerical Modeling:** Validated and optimized simulations to evaluate thermal behavior, efficiency, cost, and discharged energy.
- **Performance Insights:** Demonstrated up to a 250% increase in energy density with PCM integration, highlighting trade-offs between cost and performance.
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Conducted scientific visits, presented findings at seminars, and drafted a research paper to disseminate outcomes.

These accomplishments contribute to scalable, cost-effective TES solutions for renewable energy.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

My TNA experience went smoothly with people from the host research infrastructure being cooperating and providing what is needed.

Intended publications

The outcomes of this project is expected to be published in the form of conference or journal publication.

Data management

All data used in this work is stored and managed by the user.

Conclusions / additional comments

Nothing to be added

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Comment: I tried to submit the questionnaire twice, but it seems not working properly as can be seen in the screenshot below.

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
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Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
<i>Potentially allow for longer TNA period +12 weeks</i>											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										

Personal experience		Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support?				
		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?		1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>No answer</i>						

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

I have read the [StoRIES privacy policy](#) for participation in the StoRIES TNA and consent to participation and the associated data processing.

Date of submission to StoRIES TNA team: 23/12/2024

Your full name:

Your signature: